

RISING AGAINST TERROR: REGIONAL STRATEGIES IN ASIA AND AFRICA AMID GLOBAL THREATS

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Abstract: While incidences of terrorism is a long-aged movements that had a common history with human experience, the today terrorist activities across the world has remained a significant global phenomenon. The study observed that terrorism has followed different waves over time and space that has historically manifested traced back between the 11th and 13th century to the present modern-day world. With a special reference to Asia-Africa terrorism incidences, the study observed that terrorist activities across these regions have posed a serious problem on human population for centuries while in particular, the activities of the modern day terrorist groups are noticeable across these regions inspiring or interwoven with the cumulative outcome generated from the interface of political, economic, religious, ideological, social, psychological and global issues as well as emotions and other factors. The study discusses some of the noticeable extremist/terrorist groups across the Africa, Asia, Middle-East and SouthEast Asia countries particularly those that have been designated by United Nations and highlighted some of the regional counterterrorism measures mechanisms put in place to sustain the pace for peace and security of the regions. The study suggested a stiffer regional responses to counterterrorism to include the use of violence to fight and depose the terrorists and the use international regional organizations, joint-tasks and conventions to introduce more international norms in opposing terrorism in addition to the existing roles of United States who had continually providing logistics support, intelligence training, advisors and equipment both security equipment and relief materials in support of the wide range stabilization efforts, such as defection, demobilization, disengagement, de-radicalization, and reintegration programming in the affected regions.

Keywords: Counterterrorism, Extremisms, Terrorist Activities, Regional Organizations.

Introduction

against every states, leaders and head of territories or Extremism, terrorism and radicalization has existed for empires including others who had governed a very long time, it is a common phenomenon in human society that has persistently manifested violently throughout human history¹. Although, the word 'terrorism' is a contested concept and number of reports, definitions and assumptions has firmly

¹ Jensen, Richard Bach (2023) "The First Global Wave of Terrorism and International Counter-Terrorism, 1905-14."

showed different forms of manifestation of the terrorist activities across the globe². Terrorist activities is characterized by the calculated use of unlawful violence or threat of unlawful violence to inculcate fear; intended to coerce or to intimidate governments or societies in the pursuit of goals that are generally political, religious, or ideological³⁴. It is also been regarded as the use of force to achieve psychological effects in a particular target audience.

The act of terrorism is not unique to the 20th and 21st centuries. Terrorism had existed in 18th century revolutionary France during the reign of terror, as well as among the Zealots of Palestine in opposition to Roman rule some 2000 years ago⁵. Terrorism in this situation is characterized by the use of violence against civilians, with the expressed desire of causing terror or panic in the population. Terrorism today has become an issue of concern for the whole world in general. This is because the continuous devastating influence of terrorism is felt everywhere across all the continents while every races of the world are also terribly having their own proportion felt in violent terrorist activities as the case maybe. Over time and space, terrorism has been linked or interwoven with the cumulative outcome generated from the interface of political, economic, religious, ideological, social, psychological and global issues as well as emotions and other factors⁶. This interface has manifested itself across the globe with a special reference to the Asia-Africa terrorist activities where the various indices of terrorist activities has showed that terrorism has remained a significant and serious problem on human population.

The Global Waves of Terrorism, a Brief History

Terrorism is a regular incident in our contemporary world. The incidence has followed different waves that has historically manifested traced back between the 11th and 13th century to the present modern-day world⁷. The table below indicated the global waves of terrorism accordingly.

² What is Terrorism?" Terrorism Research, 2017.

³ Shughart, William (2006) "An Analytical History of Terrorism,

⁴ -2000." In Public

⁵ Migaux, Philippe (2016) "Al Qaeda." In The History of Terrorism: From Antiquity to ISIS,

⁶ ibid

⁷ Gupta, Dipak (2011) "Waves of International Terrorism: An Explanation of the Process by which Ideas Flood the World. Choice 128, no. 7 (2006):

The Global Waves of Terrorism

Waves	Catalyst	Goals	Targets	Tactics	Reason for Declines
Assassins: Between 11 th and 13 th century	Ismailism movement	Assassinations of persons associated with power	political and religious leaders	Assassination	Destroyed by the Mongolian
French Revolution 1793 – 1794	Reign of Terror'	Violence acts and intimation against the government's enemies	Oppositions to the government	mass executions by guillotine	End of Regime
Anarchist 1870s – 1910s	Slow political reform, declining legitimacies of monarchies	Revolution, eliminate government oppression	Heads of government	Assassinations using dynamite, bank robberies	Aggressive state opposition, beginning of World War I
Nationalist 1920s – 1960s	Versailles Peace Treaty, increased desire for self determination	Eliminate colonial rule, create new state	Police and military	Guerilla style hit and run attacks	Achieved goals, colonial rulers Withdrew from territories
New Left 1960s – 1980s	Vietnam War, Cold War tensions	Eliminate the capitalist system	Governments, increased focus on U.S.	Hijackings, kidnappings, assassinations	End of Cold War
Religious 1979 – 2020s (predicted)	Iranian Revolution, new Islamic century, Soviet invasion of Afghanistan	Creation of global Islamic Caliphate	U.S., Israel, Europe, mass transportation systems, public venues	Suicide bombings, aircrafts and vehicles as weapons	-

Rapoport (2013)

Historically, the 11th and 13th century's terrorist activities emerge from the Ismailism movement rooted in the region of Syria and Iraq⁸. Assassination was a common method of terrorist activities during this time while particularly, the targets people for assassinations were mostly individuals or group of persons associated with power and precisely because they are figureheads and number of both political and religious leaders were assassinated during this period⁹. This is more reasons the group is called Assassins terrorist organization with much in common features of the twenty-first century terrorism. The Assassins terrorist organization were considered to be the best organized terrorist group to have lived and operated for close to two centuries before they were destroyed by the Mongolian, an East Asia state and ethnic group bordered by China and Russia in 1276.¹⁰ Although, terrorist organizations has not been adjudged to be specifically Islamic or Middle east problem or that is limited to the region.

Across the globe, there are some other indices of terrorist act that can also be traced back to the two or three past centuries in some region. For example, the terrorist act in Europe. This is manifested in the clarifications according to scholars like Hegel who saw the insight followed by the French Revolution of 1789 as the spring board of terrorism. Accordingly, French revolution is said to have marked the beginning of modern terrorism and the turning point in the historical perspectives to terrorism. It was also said that the French Revolution was the period upon which the term 'terrorism' was etymologically derived because of the 'Reign of Terror' that occurred or accomplished with the revolutionary government of Maximillian Robespierre and the Jacobin party¹¹ who heatedly employed violence acts to systematically intimidate the regime's enemies and suppress opposition to the government some of which include mass executions by guillotine. Here, the act of 'terror' which is also synonymous to the act of 'state terrorism' and termed reign of terror majorly between 1793, and 1794 has equally gave rise to the modern day terrorism.

The history according to the modern terrorism started with anarchist movement in Russia between 19th and spread throughout Europe and into the Balkan states through 20th centuries. A book titled "Defense against Terrorism" written by Duyan in 2012 traced the history to the waves of modern time terrorism into four waves. The first wave stated around 1890 and 1920 when the act of terrorism was based on ideological and revolutionary motivations. This period, the revolutionaries also referred to the anarchist group existed in Russia as Russian Narodnaya Volya also popularly known as 'people's will movement'¹². This period as against the French Revolution period of 1789 of state terrorism, the Russian Narodnaya Volya anarchist movement served as the development of individual terrorism

⁸ Shughart, William (2006). "An Analytical History of Terrorism, 1945-2000." In Public Choice 128, no. 7 (2006): 7-39.

⁹ ibid

¹⁰ Jensen, Richard Bach (2013) "The First Global Wave of Terrorism and International Counter- Terrorism, 1905-14."

¹¹ Moran, Michael. (2016) "Terrorist Groups and Political Legitimacy." The Council on Foreign Relations. March 16, 2006.

¹² Gupta, Dipak (2011) "Waves of International Terrorism: An Explanation of the Process by which Ideas Flood the World."

where selective terror was used against individual or groups in order to bring the government of the day down. This period, kings were assassinated including every other notable leaders around the time (1890 and 1920). One of the notable anarchist act this period was the assassination of the Arch duke Ferdinand Franz and his wife in Sarajevo in and 1914 whose assassination in Sarajevo is considered the most immediate cause that led to the crisis precipitated Austria-Hungary's declaration of war against Serbia, which in turn multiple effects triggered series of events that eventually led to declaring war that started the first World War (WW1) Another wave was an Anticolonial wave between 1920 and 1970 when terrorist tactics and strategies changed from elimination of the prominent personalities and particularly top government officials became difficult or result was not effective. This is the period¹³ when the anarchist movement of the first waves lost grips towards the end of first quarter of 20th century and immediately after the conclusion of and Versailles Peace Treaty that ushered out by the World War I which also precipitated the second Anticolonial wave. In this anticolonial period, one of the major goals was to eliminate colonial rule using the principle of national self-determination to break up the empires of the defeated states mostly in Europe to create or establish new state or territories of independence¹⁴. In this second waves the terrorist devised a more complicated technique whereby targets were expanded strategically to eliminate police officers, military personnel and their families, being "those who protects lives and properties of the citizens". This is in addition to the continuous assassinations of top government officials during this wave¹⁵. Second wave terrorist groups used guerrilla-like tactics against troops, by employing hit and run style of attacks. In this period, separatist also assassinated numbers of political leaders including other governments' officials in the name of national self-determination to end colonialism. Prominent among those who were assassinated was a Yugoslavian king and French ministers who was assassinated by some ethnic separatists. This wave also increased the new dimension and polarization between the Western and Eastern world where transnational terrorism were used for political interest.

The other wave (third) came between 1970 through 1980 and was similar to that of first Anarchist wave, the Russian Narodnaya Volya anarchist movement where selective terror was used against individual or groups of individual in order to bring the government of the day down¹⁶. The development of the 3rd wave terrorist groups began from West after the Vietnam War of 1975 being a major event that has internationally triggered the third New Left wave of terrorism. This period, the terrorists chose to selectively targets to kidnap high profile individual in large-sum unlike the anticolonial wave whose targets are mainly political figures including military and police officers. Many of the activities of

¹³ Sedgwick, Mark (2007) "Inspiration and the Origins of Global Waves of Terrorism." In *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 30, no. 2 (2007): 97-112.

¹⁴ *ibid*

¹⁵ Rapoport, David (2013) "The Four Waves of Modern Terror: International Dimensions and

¹⁶ Migaux, Philippe (2016) "Al Qaeda." In *The History of*

Terrorism: From Antiquity to ISIS, edited by Gerard Chaliand and Arnaud Blin, 314-348. Oakland: University of California Press, 2016.

terrorist under this wave was bombings, kidnappings and frequent hijacking of Airlines particularly directed at European and American airline for hostages and for negotiations. The activities of this wave of terrorism has left more than seven hundred international airlines hijacked in first three decades of the wave while the most memorable incident of assassinations and kidnaping of high profile high profile individual/personalities is the case of Italian Prime Minister Aldo Moro, who was kidnapped and eventually murdered by the of terrorist when his government refused to enter into negotiations to meet the terrorist demands. Other prominent targets included the British Ambassador to Ireland, Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher, and Jordan's King Hussein. Rapoport noted that, the first and third wave assassinations took place for different reasons; while the first wave victims were targeted because they political figures, the third wave assassinations were carried out as punishments for acts deemed antagonistic to a group's cause of the group. Terrorism in this period was adjudged to have based on revolution, motivational ideologies, ethnic separatists and leftwing/rightwing reformist.¹⁷

The present wave came around as a religion terrorism in late 1980s/1990'. This came after the decline of the previous waves especially the leftwing/right wing and state sponsored terrorism. This type of waves was adjudged to have entirely different first time in features, scope and mechanisms from the previously terrorist activities for many reasons. The 4th wave of terrorism is a multi-national organizations dominated by religious justifications and by religion extremist. A typical example of this type of terrorist organization is Al Qaida founded in 1998 by a religion extremist¹⁸. Al Qaida is a multi-national terrorist organization whose activities posed one of the most important threats to the security of the West, in particular, the world security in general. Some of the attacks credited to this terrorist group is the attack of September 11, 2001 in America¹⁹. This attack is the most destructive attack by a terrorist organization the long bloody history of rebel, extremist or terrorism. On the other hand, after the attack of September 11, 2001, terrorism has become an endemic sprouting up from a religion fundamentalist terrorist groups such as the ISIS, Boko Haram and so many others.

United Nations Designated Asia-Africa Extremist/Terrorist Groups

Terrorism across the world has remained a significant and serious problem on human population across many countries for centuries while the activities of the modern day terrorist groups are noticeable across all the continents of the world inspiring by ideological point of view and derived from anarchism through anti-colonialism socialism and religious extremism²⁰. For example, the following terrorist organization are noticeable across Africa, Asia, Middle-East and SouthEast Asia respectively.

¹⁷ ibid

¹⁸ ibid

¹⁹ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

²⁰ Migaux, Philippe (2016) "Al Qaeda." In The History of

Terrorism: From Antiquity to ISIS, edited by Gerard Chaliand and Arnaud Blin, 314-348. Oakland: University of California Press, 2016. Consequences.

Africa

A glance at the major extremist/terrorist groups in Africa

SN	Name	Country	Establishment	Philosophy	Activities
1	AL-SHABAAB	Somalia, Kenya and Uganda	Al-Shabaab took over most of southern Somalia in 2006	To attacks in Mogadishu and in central and northern Somalia, targeting Somali government officials	Bombings, other various types of suicide attacks
2	ANSAR ALSHARIA	Libya, Tunisia	Ansar al-Sharia (AAS) is a group in Libya who emerged after the 2011 Libyan revolution	To institute a sharia and particularly to remove the influence of United State and other Western power from Libya.	Cross-border attacks, assassination and kidnappings activities targeted at foreigners
3	ANSAR BAYT AL-MAQDIS	Egypt, Sinia	Ansar Bayt al-Maqdis (ABM) emerged in 2011	Pledged allegiance to ISIL (the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant) to operate mostly in the Sinai with expansion to Egypt's Nile Valley.	Kidnapping, violent attacks and assassination
4	LORD'S RESISTANCE ARMY (LRA)	Sudan DRC CAR Uganda	Established in 1988 by Joseph Kony	An Ugandan rebel group, with the movement their operation towards the borders lines of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) and the Central African Republic (CAR) including the South Sudan	Various armed violence primarily against civilians for murder, torture, rape, and very may other damages
5	BOKO HARAM	Nigeria Chad, Niger, Cameroon	The group has existed in various forms since the late 1990s	Boko Haram started inform of a force to oppose western education	Kidnapping, violent attacks and assassination including attacks in neighboring Cameroon, Chad, Niger, as well as Nigeria.
6	AL-QA'TIDA IN THE LANDS OF THE ISLAMIC MAGHREB (AQIM)	Algeria Mali Libya	It originally formed in 1998 as the Salafist Group for Preaching and Combat (GSPC)	AQIM employs conventional terrorist tactics, including guerrilla ambushes, and mortar, rocket, and IED attacks	Kidnapping for ransom, violent attacks, assassination extortion.

Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

Terrorist group in Africa are classified according was a militant wing of the Somali Council of to their major categories²¹ as indicated in the table Islamic Courts. The group is also called Harakat above. Number one is Al-Shabaab. Al-Shabaab Shabaab al-Mujahidin and took over most of southern Somalia in 2006. Al-Shabaab has claimed responsibility for many bombings, terrorist activities such as various

²¹ "Categories of Terrorist Groups." Terrorism

Research.<http://www.terrorismresearch.com/groups/categories.php>

types of suicide attacks in Mogadishu and in central and northern Somalia, typically targeting Somali government officials. Al-Shabaab operates in Somalia, Kenya and Uganda. Another noticeable group is ANSAR ALSHARIA. Ansar al-sharia group who also operates in Tunisia emerged after the 2011 Libyan revolution²². The major goals of this group is to institute a sharia and particularly to remove the influence of United State and other Western power from Libya. This group has been suspected in terrorist activities for their involvement in attacks and kidnappings that were particularly targeted at foreigners, including other various assassinations in Libya and Tunisia respectfully²³. Another notorious group in Africa is Ansar Bayt Al-Maqdis. This group emerged in 2011 and subsequently pledged allegiance to ISIL (the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant) in 2014 following their notorious activities mostly in the Sinai with an extension to Egypt's Nile Valley. The group has been claiming responsibility for various attack in Sinai and others in sophisticated attacks in Egypt²⁴. Also in Africa is another group named Lord's Resistance Army (LRA). Although, the Lord's Resistance Army is a Ugandan rebel group, but the group has moves their operation towards the borders of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) and the Central African Republic (CAR) including the South Sudan. The group was established in 1988 by Joseph Kony. Konys LRA soldiers carried out various armed violence primarily against civilians for murder, torture, rape, and very may other damages. Another deadly terrorist group in Africa is Boko Haram. Although, Boko Haram the group has existed in various forms since the late 1990s but it came to a noticed under their former leader Muhammad Yusuf as a terrorist organization inform of a force to oppose western education in Nigeria sometimes 2009. The group is also "Jama'atu Ahl as-Sunnah li-Da'awati walJihad" (JASDJ). Their operations are noticeable in Nigeria, Chad, Niger and Cameroon. Boko Haram's operations in these countries are said to include kidnappings, particularly schoolchildren Nigeria, suicide bombing and conducting of other various attacks in neighboring Cameroon, Chad, and Niger republic²⁵. The AlQa'ida in the Lands of the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) is yet another terrorist organization in Africa. Al-Qa'ida in the Lands of the Islamic Maghreb is an Algeria-based Sunni Muslim extremist group. It originally formed in 1998 as the Salafist Group for Preaching and Combat (GSPC), a faction of the Armed Islamic Group, which was the largest and most active terrorist group in Algeria before the group officially joined al-Qa'ida in September 2006. AQIM has historically operates in Algeria, Mali and Libya ²⁶. Some of the activities of the group include kidnapping for ransom, violent attacks, assassination and extortion.

²² ibid

²³ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism."

²⁴ ibid

²⁵ ibid

²⁶ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

Asia

A glance at the major extremist/terrorist groups in Asia					
SN	Name	Country	Establishment	Philosophy	Activities
1	AFGHAN TALIBAN	Afghanistan Pakistan	Formed in early 1990s	Establishment of Islamic Emirate	Targeted bombings, assassinations and violent attacks
2	JAISH-E-MOHAMMED (JEM)	Pakistan	Founded by Masood Azhar in early 2000	To unite Kashmir with Pakistan and to expel foreign troops from Afghanistan	Use of heavy machine guns, assault rifles, mortars, improvised explosive devices, and rocket-propelled grenades to attacks.
3	LASHKAR-E-TAYYIBA (LT)	Pakistan Afghanistan	Formed in the early 1990s as the military wing of Markaz-ud-DawawalIrshad, a Pakistan-based Islamic fundamentalist missionary organization	oppose the Soviets in Afghanistan	attacks, assassinations and kidnappings
4	HAQQANI NETWORK	Afghanistan Pakistan	Founded by Jalaluddin Haqqani in mid-to-late 1990s	Sophisticated insurgent group targeting US, Coalition, and Afghan forces in Afghanistan	Extortion, kidnapping for ransom, and smuggling
5	ABU SAYYAF GROUP (ASG)	Philippines: Davao	Split from the Moro National Liberation Front in the early 1990s	Formed as a separatist groups operating in the southern Philippines and to promote an independent Islamic state in western Mindanao and the Sulu Archipelago	Engages in kidnappings for ransom, bombings, assassinations, and extortion
6	JEMAAH ISLAMIYAH (JI)	Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, Indonesia, Brunei, and the southern Philippines	Formed in the early 1990s	Formed to institute an Islamic state	Targeted bombings

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From Asia, Afghan Taliban is a Sunni Islamist nationalist and pro-Pashtun movement founded in the early 1990s that ruled most of Afghanistan from 1996 until October 2001²⁷. The group consolidated their strength in southern Afghanistan and continuously advanced operation to capture several provinces with the aimed of establishment of the the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan. Jaish-e-

²⁷ ibid

Mohammed (JEM) is another extremist group in Asia. The group is also known and called the Army of Mohammed, Khudamul Islam, and Tehrik ulFurqaan among other names with their based in Pakistan. The group was said to have founded by Masood Azhar in early 2000 to unite the Kashmir with Pakistan and to expel foreign troops from Afghanistan²⁸. The group uses light and heavy machine guns, assault rifles, mortars, improvised explosive devices, and rocket-propelled grenades in its attacks. The US State Department designated JEM a Foreign Terrorist Organization in 2001.

Another noticeable group in Asia is Lashkar-eTayyiba popularly known as Army of the Righteous. This group is one of the largest militant groups formed in the early 1990s. The group, as a military wing of Markaz-ud-Dawa-wal-Irshad, a Pakistan-based Islamic fundamentalist missionary organization was mainly aimed at opposing Soviets in Afghanistan. In 2002, the United States and United Nations designated LT an international terrorist organization. Haqqani Network is another extremist group in Asia²⁹. The Haqqani Network is also a Sunni Islamist militant organization founded in mid-to-late 1990s by Jalaluddin Haqqani, an Afghan warlord during the anti-Soviet war. Although, the Haqqani Network is based primarily in the North Waziristan of Pakistan, its operations has been noticeable across cross-border into eastern Afghanistan and Kabul. The group was said to have primarily composed of members of the Zadran tribe. The Haqqani Network has been claiming responsibility for many attacks including the June 2011 assault on the Kabul Intercontinental Hotel, conducted jointly with the Afghan Taliban, and two major suicide bombings in 2008 and 2009 respectively³⁰. Some of other places where the group had conducted their nefarious activities are in Kabul, the US Embassy, International Security Assistance Force (ISAF) headquarters, the Afghan Presidential Palace, and the Afghan National Directorate of Security headquarters against the Indian Embassy in Kabul. The group also involve in some other criminal activities in Afghanistan and Pakistan, some of which include extortion, kidnapping for ransom, and smuggling.

From the South East Asia, Abu Sayyaf Group (ASG) is an Islamic separatist group operating in the southern Philippines. The group was splintered from the Moro National Liberation Front in the early 1990s to promote an independent Islamic state in western Mindanao and the Sulu Archipelago³¹. The group generally engages in nefarious activities such as kidnappings for ransom, bombings, assassinations, and extortion in the region around Basilan, Sulu, and Tawi-Tawi Provinces with some of its activities also a presence in Mindanao, Philippines Another extremist/terrorist group noticeable in the South East Asia is JEMAAH ISLAMIAH (JI). This group, Jemaah Islamiyah (JI) was formed in the early 1990s with the purpose of instituting an Islamic state in the region³². Although, the group is an Indonesia-based group but the Jemaah Islamiyah (JI) has various secret network of terrorist

²⁸ "Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace.

²⁹ *ibid*

³⁰ Cronin, Audrey Kurth 2017: "Behind the Curve: Globalization and International Terrorism."

³¹ *ibid*

³² Rasler, Karen, and William 2011: Thompson. "Looking for

Waves of Terrorism." In

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activities spreading across Malaysia, In International Security Singapore, Indonesia, Brunei, southern Thailand and the southern Philippines. Activities of the group has been a targeted bombings mainly against Middle East

A glance at the major extremist/terrorist groups in Middle East

SN	Name	Country	Establishment	Philosophy	Status
1	AL-QA'IDA IN THE ARABIAN PENINSULA (AQAP)	Yemen Saudi Arabia	AQAP emerged in January 2009 following the unification of Yemeni and Saudi terrorist elements	Intent to serve as a hub for regional terrorism in the Arabian Peninsula	Attacks and skirmishes across the region, setting free of prisoners, robbed banks, and taken over government facilities
2	AL-QA'IDA CORE	Iran Libya Afghanistan Somalia Nigeria	Established in 1988 by Usama Bin Ladin	Expelling Western influence from Muslim countries	Kidnapping, Violent attacks, Targeted bombings and assassinations
3	HAMAS	Both Israel and the Palestinian territories	HAMAS formed in late 1987 at the beginning of the first Palestinian intifada (uprising).	The group's charter calls for establishing an Islamic Palestinian state in place of Israel	small-arms attacks, improvised roadside explosives, and rocket attacks.
4	ISLAMIC STATE OF IRAQ AND THE LEVANT (ISIL)	Iraq Syria Jordan	Established in April 2004 by Abu Mus'ab al-Zarqawi	The group targeted Coalition and Iraqi forces and civilians to pressure foreigners to leave Iraq, reduce Iraqi popular support for the US and Iraqi Government	cross-border attacks, assassination and kidnappings activities targeted at foreigners.

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Western interests' presence or interest in the region³³.

From the Middle East, Al-Qa'ida is an extremist group in the Arabian Peninsula³⁴. The group is also a Sunni extremist group based in Yemen that has orchestrated numerous high-profile terrorist attacks in the region. The group emerged in 2009 following a result of the unification of Yemeni and Saudi terrorist

³³ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace

³⁴ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

elements which has also gesticulating two groups as regional terrorism in the region, Arabian Peninsula. The group has undertaken a number of attacks that are particularly targeted Yemeni Government and since regularly engage in attacks and skirmishes across the region to freed prisoners, robbed banks, and taken over government facilities³⁵. Another one of the terrorist group of the Middle East is popularly known as AlQa'ida. Al-Qa'ida is formed in 1988 by Usama Bin Ladin with some other Arabs extremist who had previously fought in Afghanistan against the Soviet Union³⁶. The main goal of this group to establish a panIslamic caliphate throughout the Muslim world. Al-Qa'ida also has it to unite all Muslims towards fighting the West with a special reference to the United States of America. In addition to this, the group also aimed at expelling every Western influence from all Muslim countries. The group has advanced a number of successful terrorist activities together with all its affiliates across Iran, Libya, Somalia, Nigeria and Afghanistan. Another noticeable terrorist group in the Middle East is known as Hamas³⁷. The group was formed in the late 1987 at the beginning of the first Palestinian intifada (uprising). The group is linked its origin to the Palestinian group branch popularly known as Muslim Brotherhood which was gained its support by the sociopolitical structure of the Palestinian territories.

The philosophy of the group is to establish an Islamic Palestinian state in place of Israel. HAMAS has conducted numerous anti-Israel attacks across Israel and including the Palestinian territories since its establishment targeting civilians population, with the use of small-arms attacks, improvised roadside explosives, and rocket attacks³⁸. Another noticeable extremist group found in the Middle East is known as Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) and acronym ISIS. ISIL is a metamorphosed group who was formerly known as al-Qa'ida in Iraq and later became the Islamic State of Iraq. The group was established in April 2004 by Abu Mus'ab al-Zarqawi. The group pledged allegiance to Usama Bin Ladin with a mandate of reducing Iraqi popular support for the US and Iraqi Government. The activities of the group include cross-border attacks, assassination and kidnappings activities targeted at foreigners³⁹.

The Effects, Measures and the 'Asia-Africa' Regional Counter-Terrorism Efforts.

Africa

Countries across African continent have been employing regional organizations mechanisms to sustain the pace for peace and security of the continent. Many efforts of counterterrorism as well has been formulated against the various threats to security. For example in East Africa, the Sahel, and the Lake

³⁵ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace

³⁶ ibid

³⁷ Rasler, Karen, and William 2011: Thompson. "Looking for Waves of Terrorism." In Terrorism, Identity and Legitimacy

³⁸ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

³⁹ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace

Chad region, emphasis have been intensified on preventing the expansion of terrorist groups, affiliates, and associated organizations into new operating areas and possibly to make them unpopular in West Africa and Southern Africa⁴⁰. Although in East Africa, al-Shabaab are still very active and still have access to recruits, resources with the control of some part of the Somalia. Apart from this, Somalia seems to be a safe haven for the al-Shabaab terrorist group through which it moves freely and launched external operations attacks in neighboring Kenya and sometimes Uganda. The alShabaab affiliation is linked to the al-Qa'ida, a deadly terrorist group in Afghanistan and Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (Isil) based in Iraq respectively⁴¹. To minimally reduce the activities of the terrorist groups in the region, the African Union Mission in Somalia (AMISOM) coopted the Somali security forces with the United States to formed coordinated counterterrorism force and exert pressure on alShabaab. And the United States has continually showed support towards partnerships with East African region and across the Horn of Africa in their various efforts particularly to build coordinated counterterrorism capacity to interdict translational terrorist activities and other related-extremism⁴².

In another development, the efforts have also been strengthened to reduce the various activities of terrorism in the Lake Chad region to counter the split of Boko haram and the affiliation of ISIS in West Africa (ISIS-WA) terrorizing the region. The two groups who have also collaborated and rebranded their name as Islamic State of West Africa Province 'ISWAP'. This combined group has been found conducting several attacks across Nigeria, along with its neighbors Cameroon, Chad, Niger, and Benin Republic⁴³. Many of these attacks were majorly conducted against the civilians, the governmental body, and security forces some of which has resulted in deaths, injuries, abductions, capturing and destruction of properties with more adverse effects in Nigeria, especially in northeaster Nigeria where attacks have displaced more than two million people and left roughly 10 million in need of humanitarian assistance. Arising from this, the United States has continued to provide logistics support, intelligence training, advisors and equipment both the relief and security equipment's to Lake Chad region countries and supported a wide range of stabilization efforts, such as defection, demobilization, disengagement, deradicalization, and reintegration programming⁴⁴. In the broader region of Sahel, the activities of terrorist groups are also noticeable across norther, central and Eastern Mali and extended across Burkina Faso, and Niger republic. The terrorist activities in this region was said tom have an affiliation with al-Qa'ida and

ISIS such include 'Jama'at Nasr al-Islam wal

⁴⁰ Pillar, Paul R. 2001: "Terrorism and U.S. Foreign Policy."

Washington, D.C.: Brookings, 2001,

⁴¹ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

⁴² ibid

⁴³ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace

⁴⁴ Pillar, Paul R. 2001: "Terrorism and U.S. Foreign Policy."

Washington, D.C.: Brookings, 2001,

Muslimin' (JNIM) and ISIS-Greater Sahara (ISIS-GS), respectively. The operation of the terrorist groups in this region is deadly with annual increase of about 250 percent since 2018⁴⁵.

In a similar vein, suspected terrorist activities are also taking place across central and southern Africa. For example, there are persistent terrorist attacks in the eastern Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) linked to ISIS Allied Democratic Forces (ADF) terrorizing the Congolese civilians including the UN peacemakers/peacebuilder in DRC. This is also similar to the persistent suspected terrorism-related incidences in Mozambique and South Africa some of which are also affiliated to the activities of ISIS in these region which has resulted in the deaths of numbers of civilians in the last few years with many internally displaced persons⁴⁶. Meanwhile, the concern countries have remained strong to work against the terrorism. This has facilitated numerous mechanisms some of which is called G5 Sahel Joint Force (Burkina Faso, Chad, Mali, Mauritania, and Niger) launched in 2017 to coordinate counterterrorism operations among member countries. This G5 in the Sahel region was formed inform of counterterrorism coordination mechanism to disrupt the growing space of terrorist activities and their footprint across the Sahel region⁴⁷. This is also similar to the counterterrorism measure putting in place across central and the southern Africa.

The Middle East and North Africa

The Middle East and North African nations are also plagued with varied degree of terrorist activities across their countries⁴⁸. Among the terrorist groups in this region apart from affiliation groups are Al-Qa'ida and the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) also known and acronym as ISIS. The activities of these terrorist in the Middle East region remained resilient and actively reconstitute its capabilities and maintain safe havens amid fragile political and security climates, particularly in Egypt, Libya, Syria, and Yemen. Arising from this, the Middle East and North African nations are also been putting their best to curtail the terrorist activates across the region⁴⁹. For example, the Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia once jointly employed counterterrorism operations in the last few years to thwart the activities of ISIS and other terrorist groups on their region. While the Algerian security forces was successful in the massive arrest of the members of these terrorist groups, Tunisia has continuously showed increased in its successful counterterrorism operations some of which include the killing one of the prominent leader in the group ' Jund al-Khilafah's leader'. Similarly, Libya uses extra strategies by employing the role of 'nonstate' actors and militia group to conduct underground operations against

⁴⁵ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

⁴⁶ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace

⁴⁷ Pillar, Paul R. 2001: "Terrorism and U.S. Foreign Policy." Washington, D.C.: Brookings, 2001

⁴⁸ Rasler, Karen, and William 2011: Thompson. "Looking for Waves of Terrorism." In Terrorism, Identity and Legitimacy

⁴⁹ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace

the terrorist groups in the region and particularly to neutralize the threat posed by presence of the ISIS, al-Qa'ida and including others affiliated terrorist groups in the region. The role played by the United States in the regions against the terrorist groups is also vast. The United States has been assisting the region in the conducts of precision airstrikes aimed at the various terrorist group in the region, particularly airstrikes to eliminate the key personnel of the terrorist groups in the Libya region⁵⁰.

In Yemen, although the al-Qa'ida in the Arabian

Peninsula (AQAP) with affiliation to ISIS's Yemen has continued destabilizing the region by exploiting the security vacuum and taken the advantages arising from the ongoing crisis of conflict between the Republic of Yemen Government and Iran-backed

Houthi militants in the region⁵¹. Although, Iran Islamic

Revolutionary Guard Corps Ground Forces (IRGCQF) has been continuously accused of using advance their interests across the region by creating instability, fomenting violence and creating instability in the Middle East.

The operation of the group has also involved the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's most important oilprocessing facilities and including the active involvement of IRGC-QF in perpetual conflicts between Iraq and Syria. It was also said that IRGC-QF

through Iran has continued to promote other several U.S.-designated terrorist groups in the region by providing them with funds, weapons, training and equipment to aid their operations. Among these extremist terrorist groups across the region are Hizballah, Hamas, Palestine Islamic Jihad, Kata'ib Hizballah (KH) in Iraq, and al-Ashtar Brigades in Bahrain including the Taliban in Afghanistan and the Shia militant groups in Ira against the Houthis in Yemen⁵².

However, the countries in these region has continued to take important steps to combat the activities and spread of terrorism. This is followed by the third U.S.Qatar Counterterrorism Dialogue in few years back where Memorandum of Understanding drafted, committed and signed against the terrorist activities in the region. This MOU has also facilitated the increase in U.S.-Gulf multilateral collaboration to counter terrorism by imposing sanctions against an individuals or entities affiliated in one way or the other with terrorsupport networks in the Middle East⁵³. In a similar development, countries in the Middle East and North Africa have been collaborating with the United States to co-lead the Terrorist Financing Targeting Center (TFTC) to counter terrorist activities and terrorist financing in the region.

⁵⁰ Pillar, Paul R. 2001: "Terrorism and U.S. Foreign Policy." Washington, D.C.: Brookings, 2001

⁵¹ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

⁵² Moran, Michael 2016: "Terrorist Groups and Political Legitimacy." The Council on Foreign Relations. March 16, 2006.

⁵³ Pillar, Paul R. 2001: "Terrorism and U.S. Foreign Policy." Washington, D.C.: Brookings, 2001

East, South and Central Asia

The governments across East, South and Central Asian countries have also been taken several measure to salvage the regions against the various activities of terrorisms in their respective nations. This is aimed at reducing the persistent attacks by the terrorist groups. For example, in Philippine where multiple suicide bombings has become the order of the day as a new phenomenon for the region some of which was directed against a military unit in Sulu as well as a suicide attack at the Jolo Cathedral in Sulu, carried out by an Indonesian couple⁵⁴. Other attacks are also often directed to target religious minorities in the region together with other human rights activists across the region. Also, the continued terrorist activity in Afghanistan, Pakistan and other, East, South and Central Asia countries in few years back was said to be punctuated by a major volatile mix of insurgents groups, extremist attacks and terrorisms. Although the al-Qa'ida in Afghanistan and Pakistan has been seriously monitored and degraded, the key figures among group including some important leaders and their regional affiliate al-Qa'ida in the Indian Subcontinent (AQIS) has continued to operate from remote locations in the region that historically served as safe havens⁵⁵. A similar to this is Pakistan where some regionally focused extremist/terrorist groups were harbored/hidden to carry out their transnational activities such as the Afghan Taliban before their recently overthrown of Afghanistan government. Another similar group performing similar activities using Pakistan as a safe haven is the Haqqani Network (HQN), a group targeting India with others affiliated front organizations of Jaish-e-Mohammed (JeM), who operate from the territory⁵⁶. Although against this background, the Pakistan however did make some positive contributions to the Afghanistan peace process, such as encouraging Taliban reductions in violence. Also, Pakistan had also made some progress towards meeting the Action Plan requirements for the Financial Action Task Force (FATF) an Asian/Pacific group on anti-money laundry for combating terror financing measures⁵⁷.

However, authorities in East Asia countries, Australia, Fiji, Japan, the Republic of Korea, Malaysia, New Zealand, the Philippines, Singapore, and Taiwan have showed concern in relation to the terrorist activates in the region and therefore actively cooperating and participating in the regional and international efforts to counter terrorism by partnering in the Global Coalition to Defeat ISIS and others affiliated extremist/terrorist groups in the region⁵⁸. In this regards, Australia, China, Indonesia, Japan, and New Zealand became a member of the Global-Coalition and Counterterrorism Forum GCTF to fight the activities of the terrorist groups while GCTF was also created a Working Group, Countering Violent

⁵⁴ Annex of Statistical Information: Country Reports on Terrorism 2015

⁵⁵ Global Terrorism Index 2015: Measuring and Understanding the Impact of Terrorism." Institute for Economics and Peace

⁵⁶ *ibid*

⁵⁷ Pillar, Paul R. 2001: "Terrorism and U.S. Foreign Policy." Washington, D.C.: Brookings, 2001

⁵⁸ *ibid*

Extremism (CVE) as sub-group from the body of GCTF for the purpose of countering violent extremism movements across the region. Some of their action include strengthen the legal and security frameworks across their countries⁵⁹. Others activities by the East, South and Central Asian countries in combating terrorism include increase in regional cooperation and information sharing to investigate, arrest and prosecute terrorism cases in the region and to address some other critical trans-border border security challenges⁶⁰. The regional cooperation among the countries across this region has resulted in high numbers of terrorism-related arrests and, in very many cases, successful prosecutions. For example few years ago in Indian, the Unlawful Activities Prevention Act of 1967 was amended to allow the authorization of designating individuals as terrorists including the amendment by the Indian Parliament of National Investigation Agency (NIA) Act of 2008 to provide the NIA the ability to investigate terrorism cases overseas. This was massively assisted in by designating four terrorists within the shortest period of time including designation and investigation of some of the leaders of the extremist/terrorist groups in the region. While the United States continues to build its strategic partnership with the Government of India through the bilateral Counterterrorism policies, the United States has continually supporting the overall goals of salvaging the East, South and Central Asia regions against the various activities of terrorisms⁶¹. This is in tandem with other various Chinese government's repressive approach to counterterrorism efforts in the region⁶². The China's counterterrorism (CT) efforts has also continue to focus primarily on "extremists" and has detained more than one million extremist/terrorist on the pretext counterterrorism measures.

Conclusion

Terrorism across the world has remained a significant problem on human population across many countries for centuries while the activities of the modern day terrorist groups are noticeable across all the continents of the world inspiring by ideological point of view and derived from anarchism through anti-colonialism socialism and religious extremism. The incidence has followed different waves that has historically manifested traced back between the 11th and 13th century to the present modern-day world. The history according to the modern terrorism started with anarchist movement in Russia between 19th and spread throughout Europe and into the Balkan states through 20th centuries. The recent/present wave came around as a religion terrorism in late 1980s/1990'. This came after the decline of the previous waves especially the leftwing/right wing and state sponsored terrorism. This type of waves was adjudged to have entirely different first time in features, scope and mechanisms from the previously terrorist activities for many reasons.

⁵⁹ Reding, et.al 2014: "Handling Ethical Problems in Counterterrorism: An Inventory of Methods to Support Ethical Decision making." RAND Europe. 2014.

⁶⁰ ibid

⁶¹ Pillar, Paul R. 2001:"Terrorism and U.S. Foreign Policy."

Washington, D.C.: Brookings, 2001

⁶² Reding, et.al 2014: "Handling Ethical Problems in Counterterrorism: An Inventory of Methods to Support Ethical Decision making." RAND Europe. 2014.

This current wave of terrorism is a multi-national organizations dominated by religious justifications and by religion extremist that are noticeable across the globe with a special reference to Africa, Asia, MiddleEast and South-East Asia respectively. Arising from the devastating effects of terrorist activities across these regions (Africa, Asia, Middle-East and SouthEast Asia) the study conclude that countries around these regions should intensify more efforts at formulating different counter terrorism measures and employing regional organizations mechanisms to sustain the pace for peace and security of the continent.

The study recommends that some of number of responses be adapted to include the use of violence to fight and oppose the terrorists' organizations in the region. Also the use of international regional organizations and conventions should be directed to give affirmative policies that would create international norms in opposing terrorism in the regions. In addition to this, the United Nations should join hand with the United States on its current activities of tracking down the terrorist groups and also to improve in providing logistics support, intelligence training, advisors and equipment both security equipment and relief materials to supported a wide range of stabilization efforts, such as defection, demobilization, disengagement, de-radicalization, and reintegration programming in the affected regions.

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